

TEACHING STUDENTS ABOUT GENETIC CONNECTIONS IN SCHOOL EDUCATION IS THE MAIN ELEMENTS OF SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8431490>

Abstract. Appropriate formation of scientific concepts in school education, while teaching students about genetic connections are the main elements of scientific knowledge. As a result of the formation of knowledge about the environment to students with the help of chemical experiments, they will have a conscious understanding.

Key words: *chemistry, experience, scientific, understanding, knowledge, connection, education, method.*

Experiments, which are of great importance in chemistry, also play an important role in teaching its basics at school. Chemical experiments in a school chemistry course have some scientific differences, but are similar in many ways. It should be noted that showing or performing experiments during the teaching process allows students to get to know not only the phenomena themselves, but also the methods of chemistry. In addition, new theories and new concepts are formed on the basis of experience.

This is due to the fact that the chemical experiment has a number of unique properties. They include: exponentiation, the ability to observe not only the result of the process, but the process itself, short duration, ease of organization and conduct, uncertainty, the ability to conduct comparative, group and other forms of experiments, multivariate, etc. enters.

The experiment is a means of preventing the mistakes of learners and correcting their knowledge, and becomes a source of mastery of further experiments.

It is used to check the correctness of the put forward hypotheses, to solve problems in the educational process. Through chemical experiments, students learn about substances and the changes that occur with them, and gain the evidence they need to make comparisons, generalizations, and conclusions.

Experience, which is a way of knowing chemical objects and phenomena, simultaneously serves as an undeniable proof of the objectivity of scientific knowledge about the world, the openness of the world to human knowledge, and the possibility of changing nature. In this regard, the method and means of teaching carried out by conducting experiments perform developmental,

educational (didactic) and educational tasks, and serve to form the scientific worldview of students [1]. In the modern conditions of implementation of the principles that develop and improve education, for example, heuristic, corrective, generalizing, research and other methods can also be characteristic of it [2].

The content of educational chemical experiments includes: a) chemicals and their properties; b) chemical transformations, their characteristics in certain conditions; c) causal relationships between events; g) the validity of the laws and theories made as a result of logical conclusions based on experiments or general theoretical rules, etc. are relevant. All the indicated cases of experimental work are directly related to the formation of chemical concepts.

Chemical concepts are generalized knowledge about important signs of chemical phenomena and processes, which are formed on the basis of their perception. Their analysis makes it possible to determine the important properties common to all of them and to define chemical laws on this basis. The empirical nature of chemistry is manifested, first of all, in the need for each scientific concept to be logically derived from the task and grounded in practice.

The process of mastering definitions by students is a kind of general cognitive process, which is carried out step by step according to the following scheme: perception → thinking → abstract thinking → practice.

Here, the role of chemical experiments taught at school is particularly important in the formation of both empirical and theoretical concepts.

Chemical experiments are closely related to the studied theory, on the basis of which experimental data are summarized, they serve as a basis for the formation of specific chemical concepts. In this process, we can distinguish the following main types of correlation between experience and theory[2]:

1. Experiment is the main way of forming empirical concepts and their systems, signs of reactions, chemical properties, groups and classes of substances.
2. It serves as a combination of experience and theory in forming a system of knowledge about chemical reaction and chemical production.
3. Theory is the source of education, the basis of explanation. Experiment is a way to confirm the correctness of predictions and conclusions.
4. While theory plays a leading role, experience, especially mental and auxiliary, is important.

At the same time, it should be noted that the final stage of knowledge is the clarification of generalized knowledge directly related to practice.

It follows that, from the point of view of epistemology, the formation of ideas and definitions about substances and their changes on the basis of theoretical generalizations in the course of chemistry cannot be carried out without their precise observation and experiments. Perception begins with sensing and perceiving concrete objects, events, processes, evidence, and then moves to generalization and abstraction. At the same time, in order to explain the nature of the observed chemical phenomena and the processes that occur during the experiment, students are required to have a deep knowledge of laws and theories.

A chemical experiment is a direct illustration and source of knowledge that helps build fundamental chemical concepts. This was emphasized by the founders of the methodology of teaching chemistry. Thus, by revealing the nature of the cognitive process, it becomes clear that it is impossible to teach chemistry without empirical acquaintance with matter and chemical processes. In the practice of teaching chemistry, two methods of forming ideas and concepts are used. The first is the observation of substances and their chemical changes by students, the second is oral description, studying the text of a book or diagrams, Tables are distinguished by the perception of models. But ultimately, the second way is based on the experience gained with the first way, because the indirect way of forming ideas and concepts requires clear images and developed imagination.

The most important means of understanding chemical phenomena is the central role of experience in the educational process, because when observing and conducting experiments, students learn not only substances and the changes that occur, but also compare, generalize, draw conclusions. they also acquire the necessary evidence for

Many Methodists argue that there should be a balance between evidence and theory taught in a chemistry course. Evidence (experience) should be the basis for learning the theory and confirm it. Theory must be used to predict evidence, "...an over-enthusiasm for theories can lead to scholastic imaginings rather than progress"[3].

Naturally, it is impossible to form students' chemical concepts without including these concepts in the study of the educational process. In addition to empirical verification, it is impossible to determine whether a given system of definitions, theories, laws is objectively a true theory or another system.

Sensations and perceptions formed as a result of a chemical experiment should be closely related to the mental activity of students. Thinking based on

feelings and perception should establish connections and connections between the objects and events of the objective world in connection with the formation of experience, lead to generalization, abstraction, and the formation of deep scientific concepts.

Thus, the acquisition of concepts is inextricably linked with the development of students' thinking. Here, the chemical experiment has great potential, because the collection of evidential materials on its basis helps to perform important mental operations: comparison, generalization, systematization, conclusion, etc.

Summarizing all of the above, we can draw the following conclusions:

1. Chemical experience is a source of knowledge, a unique method and means of understanding chemical objects and the surrounding reality, and occupies an important place in the educational process.

2. Forming ideas and concepts about substances and their changes on the basis of theoretical generalizations in the course of chemistry cannot be done without actual observation and experience.

3. Observing substances and reactions with their participation, describing and explaining phenomena, predicting and discussing chemical evidence, combining chemical experiments and related calculation tasks, independently performing various chemical experiments - all this gives students what they have learned helps to understand and correctly master, evaluate the variety of chemical material, substances.

Foydalanilgan ajabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Верховский В.Н. Техника химического эксперимента. - М.: Просвещение, 1973. - Т. 1. - 368 с.39.
2. Вивюрский В.Я. Эксперимент по химии в средних профтехучилищах. - М.: Просвещение, 1980. - 71 с.41.
3. Кузнецова Н.Е. Формирование систем понятий при обучении химии. - М., 1989.- 144 с.128.
4. Чернобельская Г.М. Методика обучения химии в средней школе: Учеб пособие для студ. высш. учеб. заведений. - М.: Гуманит. изд. центр ВЛАДОС, 2000.-336 с.244.
5. Jabborov F.B. O'quv belgili axborot modellaridan foydalangan holda umumlashtirilgan kimyoviy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishda maktab o'quvchilarining o'quv-bilish faoliyatini tashkil etish. Ta'lim tizimida innovatsion jarayonlarni jadallashtirish xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari to'plami. 2021 -№ 6. B. 332-339.

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6. Jabborov F.B. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida o'quvchilarda kimyo fani mazmunida umumlashtiriladigan ko'nikmalar. Xalq ta'limi" O'zbekiston respublikasi xalq ta'limi vazirligining ilmiy-metodik jurnali № 4. 2021.

